

VALUE EDUCATION NEED TO THE DAY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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INTRODUCTION:

The twenty first century is round the corner . The nations of the world and striving utmost to bring into the lives of their people the marvels of science and technology undoubtedly human life on this planet has been greatly enriched with incredible scientific advance. Value Education means inculcating in the children a sense of humanism a deep concern for the well being of others and nation. This can be accomplished only when we instill in the children deep feeling of commitment to values that brings order security and assured progress.

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Through value education we like to develop the social, Moral aesthetic and spiritual sides of person which are often undermined in formal Education.

“Good teachers radiate knowledge everywhere. They are unique divine looking personalities. They inspire the young students and prepare them to face any challenges in life. They instill in them courage, hope, confidence and a sence of victory values so that they march on the path of brilliance to achieve their destiny – A. P. J. Abdul Kalam.”

CLASSIFICATION OF VALUES:

1) Personal Values:

Personal values refer to those values which are desired and cherished by the individual irrespective of his or har social relationship.

Examples – excellence, self confidence, self motivation etc.

2) Social Values :

Social Values refer to those values which are other oriented. They are concerning to society social values are local, parochial and temporary in application.

Examples – team spirit, sympathy, freedom, courtesy etc.

3) Moral Values:

Moral Values refer to those values which are related to an individual character and personality conforming to what is right and virtuous.

Examples – honesty sense of responsibility etc.

4) Spiritual Values :

We define ethical values as perception of the within in man it arises from the inner depth dimension of man the ultimate ethical value is called spiritual values. Spiritual Values is the awareness itself.

Examples – dispassion, control of the senses, devotion to God etc.

5) Behavioral Values :

Behavioral values refer to all good manners that are needed to make our life successful and joyous.

Examples – academic, religious, modern global, moral etc.

VALUES IN ANCIENT INDIA :

Education is powerful instrument of change and progressive improvement of human behavior. In ancient India the Vedas the Upanishadas the epics manifested and upheld the values of Indian Society more importance was given to morality, honesty, duty, truth, friendship they were the themes of Indian culture, Literacy and Indian Society. The pupil could learn the first

Lesion of duty, devotion, dedication and discipline. The life of Guru used to be the role model for the disciples. Imparting values education and reformation of the society were the solemn aims and objectives. For the teachers of the ancient age.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT :

The true concept of development is the sustainability of man and environment on the entire globe by promoting harmony within humanity and between humanity and nature. Human welfare is the goal of development. Development without destruction of environment and human values is real development. Sustainable development seeks to meet the need and aspirations of the present without compromising the ability to meet those of the future. This can be done only with value – oriented human beings. For sustainable development there should be balance between science and humanity, ecology and economy, prosperity and peace. Sustainable development in –turn develop sustainability of man in particular, humanity in general. This stress the need for value – oriented education at all levels family, local, national and global.

STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT:

For sustainable development, we have to give importance for the following areas of development:

1. Development of human resources
2. Maintaining biodiversity
3. Importance of biotechnology
4. Development of rural energy technology
5. Harnessing of Solar and biomass energy
6. Gandhian concept of Gram Swaraj
7. Vocational education
8. Gardening and fanning
9. Management of Local resources by local people

10. Development of Water harvesting and conservation of natural resources.
11. Rural development
12. Cottage industries
13. A forestation
14. Development of waste lands
15. Skilled manpower development for future

The philosophy underlying all these are work is worship, unity, co-operation, humanity, harmony, morality, character, self-sufficiency, dignity of labour etc.

Everybody must attempt to understand human society, its cultural foundation, its unity and diversity, aspiration and missions. We should also balance the spirituality and science to bring harmony in the human society.

ROLE OF THE TEACHER:

Today's children and tomorrows citizens and nation's strength. They are to be endowed with courage, competence and imagination. The teacher has a vital role to play in our effort to education to national development. It is the responsibility of the teacher to guide, inspire and illumine his student, to enrich his discipline and to inculcate values which are in consonance with our cultural heritage and social objectives. Teachers should provide freedom and maintain discipline, he should be very realistic, natural and practical and inculcate values such as punctuality, honesty, truthfulness, self confidence, self reliance etc. required for healthy and happy life. Friendly relationship between the teacher and the taught is to be encouraged. They are the persons to develop a spiritual commitment towards democracy and public welfare, capacity to communicate, potential leadership with courage, decision-making, scientific temper and awareness of the world.

Values can be developed by the teacher at different levels. i.e. pre- primary to higher education through general education and vocational education. At primary ages, values are learnt through consensus. At university level, students develop values based on principles

independently as such the energy and idealism of the youth should be identified and channelized for glorious and dynamic India.

Through curricular subjects teacher could develop the important values in an integrated approach. The hidden curriculum, the school environment, personality of the teacher, functioning of the school transmits values,. School subjects will inculcate scientific, social, economic, utilitarian, cultural, moral, education, intellectual, patriotic, aesthetic, literary values etc.

Through co-curricular activities values-citizenship, sympathy, empathy, courtesy, equality, tolerance, self-confidence, secularism, discipline, respecting others. Dignity of labour, team spirit, accountability, forgiveness, positive attitudes towards environmental conservation obedience etc., can be developed. Values like helping aged, disabled, saving lives by donating blood, eyes, clean and green activities, gardening, healthy habits, service-mindedness, animal rearing, celebration of national festivals, awareness camps through mobile services, integration camps, helping people affected by natural calamities etc. are to be promoted by teachers at school level. Guidance programme can also be planned to develop the values, value-oriented curriculum textbooks, value-oriented training programmes for teachers at all levels, parents and administration and policy makers. Such type of programme are necessary to face new challenges in education. professional code of ethics is needed by the teacher to do justice to their roles and responsibilities and to meet professional demands. Hence teacher plays a crucial role in providing value education message for which a teacher should be a set role model.

As value-oriented education is the need of the day for all the citizens, every institution or organization should task the task of educating the public about the need for values and try to inculcate values. Mass media can be utilized as powerful weapon in this direction. But one has to evaluate whether the media is really functioning in this direction. Hence, there is a need to design the programme or issue meticulously to inculcate good human values, which helps people live with harmony and peace and to work towards developing society for a sustainable development.

CONCLUSION:

For sustainable development, we need value-based education, spiritual education, ethical education, need-based education, global education for Vasudaiva Kutumbakam, is what is necessary for making a man a human being with integrity. As all the famous, educationists visualized education is for the liberation of human mind, development of national consciousness and reconstruction of society. New education system is necessary to achieve all these and to meet new challenges. So, for sustainable development balance between science and human values is necessary, and hence value-oriented education is need of the day for all on the globe for development of integrated and balanced personalities. s

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